

RNA Silencing Mechanism and Application

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Introduction

RNA silencing also called RNA interference refers to the gene silencing effects through which gene expression is negatively regulated through non-coding RNAs such as microRNAs. RNA silencing can also be described as sequence-specific regulation of gene expression triggered by double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) (Fire et al., 1998). The mechanism by which double stranded RNA is synthesised is:

1. By the transcription of the inverted repeats in DNA into single RNA molecule that base pair with itself.
2. By the simultaneous transcription of two different complementary RNA molecules and pair with each other.
3. By the replication of double stranded RNA molecules.

RNA silencing pathways are concerned with the regulatory activity of small non-coding RNAs that function as factors involved in inactivating homologous sequences, promoting endonuclease activity, translation stoppage or DNA modification (Zhou et al., 2010). Three primary small RNA have been identified: siRNA, miRNA, piRNA.

siRNA (small interfering RNA) is non-coding double stranded RNA, acts in nucleus and cytoplasm and are involved in RNA interference. It may derive from ssRNA precursors, hairpin RNAs, enzymatically derived from non-coding RNA precursor (Ghildiyal et al., 2008).

miRNA (micro-RNA) is special class of RNAs involved in gene regulation. They are noncoding RNAs (22 nucleotide long), complementary to particular regions of mRNAs. Found in plants and animals. They promote the mRNA degradation and suppress translation. They are synthesized from initial transcription produced by RNA polymerase II and in some cases RNA polymerase III.

piRNA (piwi-interacting RNA) derived from transposon, they are the largest class of non-coding small RNA expressed in animal cells. Acts both at post-transcriptional and chromatin levels.

Mechanism

1. The best precursor to good RNA silencing is to have single stranded antisense RNA with inverted repeats which, build small hairpin RNA and panhandle constructs (Tijsterman et al., 2002)
2. The small hairpin RNA gets transported to cytosol from nucleus through nuclear exporter receptors called exportin-5, then get transformed to dsRNA. If the mechanism didn't use dsRNA but only single stranded RNA, there would be higher chance for it get hybridise.
3. The dsRNA then gets cut by Dicer into miRNA/siRNA. Dicer is endoribonuclease RNase.
4. Double stranded miRNA/siRNA separate into single strands; the antisense RNA combines with another endoribonuclease and form RISC (RNA induced silencing complex).
5. In the short sequence specific area, the mRNAs will be cut.

Early Works

It was observed that when a transgene was introduced it didn't enhance the expression of the endogenous genes, rather both got silenced. M. A. Matzke and A. J. Matzke, were engaged in genetic transformation of tobacco. When tobacco plants were transformed, first by the T-DNA-I plasmid and then by the T-DNA-II plasmid, the expression of the T-DNA-I-encoded sequences were silenced (Matzke *et al.*, 1989). They said that the promoters of the T-DNA-I were strongly methylated by the subsequent transformation with T-DNA-II. Evidence in favour of the notion that the methylation of genomic DNA can be mediated by RNA was presented several

years later from a study by Wassenecker *et al.*, (1994). The following year study was done on petunia plant for flower pigmentation. The key compound, in the metabolic pathway of petal pigmentation, is chalcone. The condensation is caused by the enzyme chalcone synthase (CHS). Napoli *et al.*, (1990) focused on CHS. the flowers of these modified plants had a wide range of pigmentation (intense purple, patterns of purple and white, and completely white). Molecular dissection of the transformed populations revealed that in some plant lines both the introduced and endogenous forms of the CHS gene were silenced to differing degrees, referred to as "cosuppression" (Napoli *et al.*, 1990; van der Krol *et al.*, 1990). Lindbo and colleagues (1993) transformed tobacco plants with the gene sequence of the tobacco etch virus (TEV) CP for TEV resistance. The Baulcombe laboratory suggested that VIGS (virus induced gene silencing) involves mRNA degradation and reported the existence of small RNA fragments during the VIGS process (Baulcombe *et al.*, 1996). But the definite proof/role of dsRNA in RNA silencing came by the study of Craig Mello, Andres Fire and associates (Fire *et al.*, 1998) with the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*.

Current Application in Plants

Transgenic papaya (*Carica papaya*) with resistance to Papaya ringspot virus (PRSV; Fuchs *et al.*, 2007 and Gonsalves *et al.*, 2007). Wang *et al.*, (2000) used RNA silencing for virus protection first in barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). Niu and colleagues (2006) used 273-bp sequence of Arabidopsis miR159a pre-miRNA transcript expressing amiRNAs against the viral suppressor genes P69 and HC-Pro to provide resistance against turnip yellow mosaic virus and turnip mosaic virus infection, respectively. Regina and colleagues (2006) used hpRNA constructs for silencing of an isoform of a starch-branching enzyme to produce a high-amylose transgenic wheat line, which if widely adopted in western countries could have vital public health benefits. Reshaping the morphine pathway in poppies (*Papaver somniferum*) to increase the yield of pharmaceutically significant compounds (Allen *et al.*, 2004). A recent report depicted that specific miRNAs are associated with disease development in pine (*Pinus spp.*) for fusiform rust infection, thus shows that the miRNA pathway may also be involved in plant interactions with fungal pathogens (Lu *et al.*, 2007).

Conclusion

There is much to learn about the molecular process of RNA silencing in plants, but our current knowledge about RNA mediated gene control mechanism has provided us a new platform for development of new molecular tools for gene function studies and crop improvement. RNA silencing has been helpful for controlling both biotic and abiotic stress in plants. RNA silencing is an optimistic approach to human kind for combating the new age challenges in agriculture with climate change being the prime concern.

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